

Standard Operating Procedures for Fluid Biomarkers
Blood, Urine, and Saliva Acquisition, Processing, Storage, Shipping

Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

A study to explore changes in cognitive, clinical, biological and digital measures following 8 weeks of twice-daily dosing of MT1988 and to evaluate safety & tolerability of MT1988, in participants at clinical high risk (CHR) for psychosis

Version 2.0, Revised 2025 November 24

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Please ensure that this is the most recent version available. Current version of SOPs are in the ProCAN SharePoint folder.
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A. LabCorp training slides and manual.....50

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
1.0	2025 Aug 7	N/A
1.1	2025 Aug 20	Pre-release: updated freezer monitoring information; updated form names; updated graphics.
2.0	2025 Nov 24	Updated pre-visit instructions for participants. Changes made to caffeine guidance and blood fasting guidance. Added guidance on recommend equipment and calibration, start-up including training and certification, freezer emergencies. Removed specifics on processing, added LabCorp slides in Appendix.

OVERVIEW

These SOPs will cover ProCAN Genetics and Fluids data collection forms, data management best practices for measuring height and weight, taking vitals (blood pressure, heart rate, temperature), point-of-care (POC) pregnancy test results, and the collection, processing, storage, and shipping of blood, urine, and saliva fluid biospecimen. **They are intended to be used in addition to the [LabCorp Manual](#), which can be found on the LabCorp Investigator Portal.**

Genetics & Fluids Core Schedule of Activities

		Study Visit Day												
		Floating Form	Screening	Day -7	Day -1	Day 1a (pre-dose)	Day 1b (post-dose)	Day 8	Day 15	Day 29	Day 43	Day 56	Day 84	Early Withdrawal
REDCap Collection Form	Height and Weight		X									X (weight only)		X (weight only)
	Vitals		X			X				X		X	X	X
	Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol				X					X		X		
	Pre Blood Draw Health Screen					X	X			X		X		X
	Blood & Urine Collection	X				X	X			X		X		X
	Pregnancy POC					X				X		X	X	X
	Blood and Urine Processing		X			X	X			X		X	X	X
	Safety Lab Review Documentation		X			X				X		X	X	X
	Labs Exclusion Criteria		X											
	Shipping Plasma for Study Drug Levels											X		X
	Freezer Deviation	X												

HEIGHT/WEIGHT FORM

A. Height

Height is measured using a stadiometer. Height is only collected at screening. Sites may use any preferred brand or type of stadiometer.

- Height is measured at the top of the head, with the subject looking straight ahead. Factors that can interfere with an accurate measurement of height include hats, certain hairstyles, such as ponytails and thick braids, and shoes. To minimize the impact of these factors:
 - Before measuring height, please ask the participant to remove hats, beanies, hoodies, headbands (religious head coverings are allowed), shoes (socks are ok). Ask the participant to undo any high ponytails or buns, if possible.

- See below for adjustments to procedure that may be needed if the participant is unable or unwilling to adjust hairstyles that interfere with use of the stadiometer.
- ⁱⁱⁱAsk the study participant to:
 - Stand with back to stadiometer.
 - Have the study participant stand with back of head, shoulder blades, buttocks, and heels against the measurement board.
 - Shoulders should be relaxed with their arms at their sides and feet flat on the ground.
 - Ask the participant to “Please stand up straight and look straight ahead”. Imagine a line drawn from the bottom of eye socket to the middle of the ear canal (Frankfurt plane). This should be parallel to floor (see diagram).
 - Place the stadiometer bar on the top of the head, compressing hair as much as possible.

Modifications for thicker hairstyles:

- For hairstyles that prevent the back of the person's head from touching the measurement board position the person slightly away from the measurement board and ensure that they are standing correctly.

▪For hairstyles that interfere with the stadiometer touching the top of the skull:

1. With the person standing correctly, with back to stadiometer, measure height to top of hairstyle using the stadiometer.
2. Next, with the person seated use a ruler or tape measure to measure distance from top of the skull to the top of the hairstyle.
3. Record the difference between the two measurements as the person's height.

Lastly, record the height, noting whether measurements are taken in inches or centimeters.

B. Weight

*Weight is measured using a physician scale. It is measured at Screening, Day 56, and in the case of Early Withdrawal. **Weight should be measured on the same scale at every visit for each participant.***

- Ask the study participant to remove shoes, jackets, sweaters, hoodies and belt.
 - Prior to a weight or vitals visit, please suggest that the participant wear a shirt under bulky outerwear so they may remove outerwear for the weight or blood pressure measurement.
 - If a participant forgets to wear an undershirt, you may ask the participant to change into a disposable gown.
 - If your site does not have a disposable gown available to them, you may continue with weight measurement and add a comment to the REDCap form that they did not remove their outerwear.
- Have the study participant empty their pockets.
- Have the study participant stand on scale.
- Record the weight, noting whether the measurements are taken in pounds or kilograms.

VITALS FORM

A. Blood Pressure and Heart Rate

According to the American Heart Association, even the smallest factors can affect a blood pressure readingⁱⁱⁱ. Because uncontrolled hypertension (defined as a systolic reading ≥ 140 mm Hg or a diastolic reading ≥ 90 mm Hg at Screening or at Day 1) is an exclusion criterion in this clinical trial, we are asking sites to follow necessary precautions so you may get the most accurate reading as possible from participants. Blood pressure and heart rate is measured using an automatic blood pressure machine and will be recorded at screening, Day 1, Day 29, Day 56, Day 84, and in the case of early withdrawal. Sites must use the same BP monitor at each visit. The recommended blood pressure monitor is the Omron 10 Series Upper Arm Blood Pressure Monitor.

Before you take a blood pressure reading, make sure you have P.A.U.S.E.D!

1. **P**lan Ahead

- The participant should avoid exercise, smoking/vaping, and caffeine for at least 30 minutes before a blood pressure reading. These reminders are located in the pre-visit instructions.

2. **U**se the restroom

- A full bladder can add 10mmHg to blood pressure. **Note: This clinical trial also requires urine sample collection, so consider having the participant provide a urine specimen immediately prior to taking blood pressure.**

3. **S**it

- Ideally, the participant should sit and relax for about five to ten minutes before you take a reading. You may suggest the participant take time to close their eyes and breathe deeply to relax.

4. **E**valuate posture & cuff placement

- The study participant should be seated on a firm chair with a flat back. Both feet flat on the ground (legs not crossed) and back supported. If needed, you may provide a step stool for the participant to comfortably rest their feet.
- The upper arm should be bare. Sites should keep disposable gowns on hand in case the participant is wearing a long-sleeve garment.
- Ensure that the blood pressure cuff is the correct size for the study participant's arm. A circumference guidance should be listed on the cuff itself. It should be fully deflated before placing it on the participant's arm.
- Wrap the cuff around the **non-dominant arm** and use the same arm for each reading throughout the study. If a participant is ambidextrous, then you may use their left arm for measurements.
- Have the participant extend their arm, **palm upward**. Line up the artery mark over the brachial artery with the bottom of the cuff about an inch above the elbow.
- **A table should fully support the lower arm WITH THE BLOOD PRESSURE CUFF AT HEART LEVEL!** You can assess that the cuff is at heart level if the arm is roughly supported at a 45 degree angle from the body, the cuff is about an inch about the elbow, and the cuff aligns with the middle of their chest.

5. **D**on't speak

- Instruct the study participant to sit quietly while their blood pressure is being taken. Start the blood pressure machine. Do not converse with the participant or fellow staff while the measurement is taking place.

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The infographic features a central illustration of a person sitting in a chair with their arm extended to a blood pressure cuff. Surrounding this central figure are seven circular callouts, each containing a specific instruction and its potential impact on blood pressure readings. The background is a solid purple color.

- USE CORRECT CUFF SIZE**
Cuff too small adds 2-10 mm Hg
- DON'T HAVE A CONVERSATION**
Talking or active listening adds 10 mm Hg
- EMPTY BLADDER FIRST**
Full bladder adds 10 mm Hg
- SUPPORT BACK/FEET**
Unsupported back and feet adds 6 mm Hg
- KEEP LEGS UNCROSSED**
Crossed legs add 2-8 mm Hg
- SUPPORT ARM AT HEART LEVEL**
Unsupported arm adds 10 mm Hg
- PUT CUFF ON BARE ARM**
Cuff over clothing adds 5-50 mm hg

Content provided by
AMA | **MAPBP**

This resource is part of AMA MAP BP™, a quality improvement program. Using a single or subset of AMA MAP BP tools or resources does not constitute implementing this program. AMA MAP BP includes guidance from AMA hypertension experts and has been shown to improve BP control rates by 10 percentage points and sustain results.

You will take **three consecutive blood pressure measurements** with at least a minute of rest in between. All three measurements will be recorded into the Vitals form, however only the last two will be averaged automatically for the “true” blood pressure.

- Record the blood pressure (higher number = systolic, lower number = diastolic) and heart rate.
- If the blood pressure is elevated (systolic ≥ 140 and/or diastolic ≥ 90) after the first measurement, check to make sure the protocol is being followed and give the person another five minutes to relax.**
 - After five minutes, restart the first blood pressure measurement and continue with the protocol.**
- Refer to the Blood Pressure Categories diagram below for a guide. Please remember that if you are not a medical professional, you cannot diagnose participants with hypertension. If you have any questions about your participant’s blood pressure, best practice is to contact your MD in the clinical trial.
- Below normal or low blood pressure will not be flagged with a warning in the data form. However, if the participant has a low blood pressure and is feeling faint or dizzy, you should contact your study doctor.

Note: Elevated blood pressure (hypertension) is defined as a **resting** systolic blood pressure of 140 or greater and/or a resting diastolic blood pressure of 90 or greater. However, it is **normal for a non-resting (such as when a person is active) blood pressure to be somewhat greater than 140/90**. This is why we ask the participant to sit and rest for at least 5 to 10 minutes before taking a reading.

Blood Pressure Categories

BLOOD PRESSURE CATEGORY	SYSTOLIC mm Hg (top/upper number)		DIASTOLIC mm Hg (bottom/lower number)
NORMAL	LESS THAN 120	and	LESS THAN 80
ELEVATED	120–129	and	LESS THAN 80
STAGE 1 HYPERTENSION (High Blood Pressure)	130–139	or	80–89
STAGE 2 HYPERTENSION (High Blood Pressure)	140 OR HIGHER	or	90 OR HIGHER
SEVERE HYPERTENSION (If you don't have symptoms*, call your health care professional)	HIGHER THAN 180	and/or	HIGHER THAN 120
HYPERTENSIVE EMERGENCY (If you have any of these symptoms*, call 911)	HIGHER THAN 180	and/or	HIGHER THAN 120

*symptoms: chest pain, shortness of breath, back pain, numbness, weakness, change in vision, or difficulty speaking

B. Body Temperature

Temperatures are taken with tympanic (ear) thermometer. The recommended brand is the Braun Thermoscan 5 Ear Thermometer.

- Check to make sure the device is operational (change batteries if needed) and be sure there is a new hygiene cover on the probe.
- Make sure the study participant's ear is free of obstructions.
 - If a participant wears an in-the-ear or in-the-canal hearing aid, ask if they would be able to momentarily remove the aid for the temperature reading.
 - Hearing aids can trap heat in the canal and raise the temperature reading. Try to wait at least 10 minutes after the aid is removed to measure the participant's temperature^{vi}.
- While wearing gloves, gently pull the participant's outer ear up and back (see diagram below). This will "straighten" the ear canal slightly.
- Using a slight rotating motion, place the probe of the thermometer into the ear canal towards the ear drum. To make sure that air temperature doesn't affect the reading, make sure the probe is inserted at least a third of the way into the canal to form a seal. The sensor should be pointing down the ear canal and not at the wall of the ear.
 - If a participant has inner ear piercings (such as a daith or tragus piercing), be sure the probe is placed and aimed past any metal.
- Turn the thermometer on and wait for it to signal the reading is complete.
- Remove the thermometer and record the temperature in Fahrenheit in the Vitals form.

TIP: If you're right-handed, it will be easier to measure temperature on the participant's right ear. If you're left-handed, use the participant's left ear. If the preferred ear is obstructed, use the opposite ear.

Note: If the body temperature is greater than or equal to 100.4°F (38°C), this indicates a fever. If it is hot outside or the person is overheated, the person's body temperature can be elevated, so if you do obtain a body temperature measurement this high, double-check that you are using the thermometer correctly and repeat the measurement. If necessary, have the participant sit quietly and try to cool down for a few minutes before re-measuring the body temperature. If the body temperature remains elevated, be sure to follow any procedures your institution has in place in case of fever.

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OVERVIEW: SALIVA SAMPLE PROCEDURES

Research Coordinators are responsible for:

- **Providing the study participants with written instructions** regarding saliva collection one week prior and reminding study participants about these instructions the day prior to saliva collection.
- Completing **Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol form** during the saliva collection visit.
- Instructing study participants about how to collect their own saliva samples, including having study participants watch a brief instructional video and correcting any deviations from passive drool sample collection instructions.
- Ensuring that **three saliva samples are collected over a two-hour period** (e.g. 1100, 1200, 1300) **preferably during the EEG**. Saliva **collection takes from three to five minutes**, thus other study procedures are to be done in between. For example, during EEG visit: Sample #1 prior to EEG capping, Sample #2 **60 minutes** after Sample #1 (during a break period), Sample #3 **120 minutes** after Sample #1, after EEG is completed.
- Samples should be collected at Minute 0, Minute 60 (+/- 10 minutes), and Minute 120 (+/- 10 minutes).
- **It is preferred to collect saliva prior to blood collection. If infeasible, try to wait at least one hour after a blood draw to start saliva collection.**
- Obtaining and preparing all saliva collection and storage materials (see [Supply List](#)).
- Ensuring that all related data collection forms are completed in full and entered into the study database.

Associated Data Collection Form (s)
Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol

Study Visit Day												
REDCap Form	Screening	Day -7	Day -1	Day 1	Day 8	Day 15	Day 29	Day 43	Day 56	Day 84	Early Withdrawal	
	Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol			X				X		X		X

PRE-STUDY VISIT INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDY PARTICIPANTS: SALIVA SAMPLES

Saliva Collection: Please provide study participants with the following information in writing at least one week prior to the study visit and again on the day before the study visit.

Instructions

You are scheduled to have saliva samples collected on **[insert date scheduled]**. To get accurate measurements from your saliva you are asked to follow some guidelines.

- The evening and morning before you come in for your appointment; please do not consume the following foods and beverages. Refrain from these foods and beverages starting at 6:00 p.m. (18:00 on the 24-hour clock) the night before giving saliva samples:
 - Dairy products (e.g. milk, cheese, etc.)
 - Alcohol
- Please be sure to get a good night's rest before your study visit.
- Please avoid rigorous exercise for 24 hours before your blood collection.
- Please don't smoke, vape, or use any other tobacco or nicotine products at least two hours prior to your study visit.
- Please do not use any marijuana or THC products on the day of your study visit.
- You may maintain your usual caffeine intake.

SALIVA SAMPLE COLLECTION FOR CORTISOL FORM

The majority of the **Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol** data collection form is completed just prior to the collection of saliva samples. The sample collection times, volumes, whether the study participant had a beverage within 10 minutes of each sample, and the storage location of each sample is collected as each saliva sample is collected. Please ensure that the required data is collected and recorded during the sample collection procedures.

Remind the study participant, *“It’s important to be honest; we understand sometimes a person can’t avoid certain activities, meds, or foods/drinks, or just forgets to follow the pre-visit instructions. It’s much better for the study to know about these things, so we can collect accurate info.”*

Instructions for reporting recent activity.

- To control for the quality of the cortisol in the sample, we need to know about the participant’s recent tobacco and marijuana use, recent exercise, dental work, and meals.
- Record whether they have consumed any alcohol or dairy products since 6pm the evening before. It sometimes helps to provide examples of foods or drinks in each category.
- If the participant recently **had a snack, meal, or beverage other than water, OR if they have brushed/flossed their teeth in the past 45 minutes**, they need to rinse their mouth out with water and wait 10 minutes before beginning sample collection.
- If they have had any **water to drink in the past 10 minutes, you should wait the full 10 minutes to begin sample collection**. This ensures the cortisol in their saliva is not diluted by water.
- To estimate diurnal variation, we need to know the time the study participant went to bed and woke up and whether this time was on the same day as the study visit or the day before the study visit.

Saliva collection instructions for study participants.

- Study participants collect their own saliva sample specimens, under your supervision. [Begin by having the participant watch the 4-minute video explaining the procedure](#). Then orient the participants to collection tubes and other supplies.
- It may be helpful to repeat the instructions, and provide any tips for saliva production (see examples in the detailed instructions below.)

Instructions for recording cryovial volumes, collection time, and cryovial rack with position

- Study participants are instructed to **provide 1 mL of saliva into the cryovial**. If study participants are not able to provide this volume, estimate the volume that they were able to provide. Record the actual volume provided.
- Record the time the study participant **ended** the passive drool saliva collection procedure for both samples.
- Record the position and rack information [per protocol](#) (see below).

SALIVA SAMPLE COLLECTION PROCEDURES

A. Workflow

B. Visit Preparation: Saliva Sample Collection

1. Collect three cryovials and three saliva collection aids from your site's supplies provided by the UNC Biospecimen Core team.
2. Remove the three cryovials for saliva collection and the three Saliva Collection Aids from the kit. Use a permanent marker to label the tubes "1," "2," and "3."
3. Pre-scan the cryovial barcodes into the appropriate data entry fields in study database (place cursor in data entry field and scan barcode on bottom of vial; scanned barcode should appear at the location of the cursor).
 - i. Pre-scanning is a very important step to make sure the proper sample is linked to the correct participant. Without it, samples may have to be thrown away, or possibly mixed up with the wrong participant.
 - ii. **Do not** pre-scan in any other data. Rack barcodes and positions should be left **blank** until you're ready to store samples in the freezer.
4. Place the cryovials in the saliva transportation rack.
5. Put ice in a small cooler marked with a biohazard label.
6. The cooler, the transportation rack of prepared cryovials, and the Saliva Collection Aids are provided to the study staff member who is responsible for collecting the saliva samples.

C. Detailed Saliva Collection Protocol

1. Collection of saliva samples:

- a. Collect the first saliva sample.
 - i. [Prior to sample collection study participants should watch the 4 minute instructional video available at the following link.](#)
 - ii. The ideal amount of saliva collected in each cryovial is **1 mL** (excluding any bubbles). If the cryovial is overfilled, **be sure to have a transfer pipet on hand** to remove some saliva before freezing.
 - iii. Study participants collect their own saliva samples. Provide the study participant with a saliva collection aid and the cryovial labeled "1". Double-check that you have provided the cryovials for the samples collected at the 1st timepoint, not at the 2nd or 3rd timepoint. Provide the study participant with a clean, flat surface to use for saliva collection. Some teams find it helpful to keep absorbent underpads on hand to place under the participant for sanitary purposes.
 - iv. Review saliva collection instructions with the study participant:
 1. Open the foil pouch and remove the Saliva Collection Aid.
 2. Remove the cap from Cryovial 1.
 3. Place one end of the Saliva Collection Aid into Cryovial 1.
 4. Ask a participant to allow their saliva to pool in their mouth (for about 10 seconds).
 5. Then, with head tilted forward, gently guide saliva through the Saliva Collection Aid into the vial. **DO NOT SPIT/BLOW** or otherwise force saliva into the tube, as this will create foaming and bubbles.

- v. On average, it should take about 3 minutes to fill one saliva cryovial. If the participant takes longer than 10 minutes to fill a sample, you can gently cut them off. If any amount of saliva is in the tube, please record volume, and continue with storage procedures.
 - vi. After the vial is filled to the required volume, remove the Saliva Collection Aid and place the aid on the clean surface.
 - vii. Attach the cap to the collection vial and tighten completely.
 - viii. Once the vial is closed and the cap is secured, use a disinfectant wipe to wipe down the outside of the collection vial.
 - ix. Once the cryovial is wiped down, place it into the transportation rack on ice.
 - x. Discard the Saliva Collection Aid and disinfect the surface.
- b. Record the end time of the first saliva collection in REDCap and set timers for 60 minutes and 120 minutes after that end time.
 - c. After 60 minutes, collect the second sample as described above and then place on ice.
 - d. After 120 minutes, collect third sample as described above and then place on ice.
 - e. The samples must remain on ice (refilling as necessary) until they are placed in the -80°C or below freezer. The samples must be placed in the -80°C or below freezer by the end of the day on the day of collection.

TIPS FOR SALIVA COLLECTION:

Participants can sometimes have a tough time with saliva collection either due to confusion, anxiety, or just general dry mouth. Based on experiences in ProNET, these are some of the tips and tricks our team has discovered.

1. Any coordinator involved in saliva collection should practice providing a saliva sample at least once during training. Experiencing it for yourself may help you explain steps to participants better.
2. Drooling in front of anyone can feel awkward! Give the participant some privacy once they understand the instructions, and check on them after about 3 minutes to look at their progress.
3. If after 3 minutes, they're finding it difficult to produce saliva, try these tricks:
 - a. Ask the participant to sit with their mouth slightly open while saliva pools in their mouth. This inhibits the urge to naturally swallow, and after about 30-60 seconds, they should have some saliva to provide a sample. Then repeat until the requested volume is reached.
 - b. Ask the participant to think about their favorite food, or better yet, if the sample is taken before lunch, ask them to think about what they might order.
 - c. With their mouth closed, ask them to try and mimic the action of sucking on a lollipop or hard candy. Try to keep the saliva towards the front of the mouth while repeating this action until there is some saliva to provide a sample.
 - d. Show the participant how to do an external salivary gland massage (see diagram below). Combine this with option A, above.

Some saliva is better than no saliva! If after 10 minutes, the participant has not reached the requested amount, please record and store what was provided. If the cryovial is completely empty, please discard and mark the sample as missing.

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Salivary gland massage

2. Storage of saliva samples:

- a. All samples must be stored at -80°C. Double-check that you have correctly recorded on the volume and all other information required of each sample in the **Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol form** before you store the samples.
- b. Place samples in the -80°C freezer according to the Saliva Sample Storage Guidelines (below). When you pull the sample storage rack out of the freezer to store the newly collected samples in it, it is extremely important that samples already stored in the storage rack do not thaw. Do not take the storage rack out of the freezer for extended times. Take it out only momentarily (<5 minutes) to add the newly collected samples, and then place back in the freezer.
- c. Directly scan the storage rack barcode into the appropriate field(s) in REDCap. Once the samples are stored in the storage rack, record on the Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol form the storage position of each sample, the time the samples are stored at -80°C, and the freezer in which the samples are stored.
 - i. **There are very few reasons why a sample should be missing or not collected.** Because samples take less than 5 minutes to collect, and are only collected three times over a short period, no samples should be skipped for time. Because some sample is better than no sample, it's always best to encourage the participant to provide at least some saliva.
 - ii. However, if a sample is not collected, or has 0 mL, please do the following:
 1. Cryovials that were not collected (0 mL) should **not** be stored in the freezer.
 2. If a saliva sample was unable to be collected, then the cryovial ID, position, and volume should all be marked as **missing** (M button in REDCap, missing or -9).
- d. After the samples are stored in the storage rack, the transportation rack must be returned to the study team.

D. Saliva Sample Storage Guidelines

Sample storage racks are provided by the Genetics & Fluids Core team. Each site will be shipped two saliva storage racks with 96 cryovials which will take care of each of the 10 participant's saliva visits. All three of a participant's saliva cryovials collected at a single visit will be stored in the same rack. Samples will be stored as shown in the guide below. Note the following:

- Rows A, C, E, and G intersect with even numbers (e.g., A2, A4, A6, A8, A10, A12, etc.)
- Rows B, D, F, and H intersect with odd numbers (e.g., B1, B3, B5, B7, B9, B11, etc.)

Please be extra attentive when recording the storage position of each sample to ensure that you are recording the correct storage position. Always record positions in a "letter number" format.

OVERVIEW: BLOOD AND URINE SAMPLE PROCEDURES

Please refer to the [LabCorp Manual](#) for detailed instructions on blood and urine collection and processing.

Study Research Coordinators are responsible for:

- **Providing study participants with written instructions** regarding the blood draw one week prior to study visit and reminding the study participants about these instructions the day prior to the blood draw.
- Completing the **Pre Blood Draw Health Screen form** (including collection of **Vitals**) prior to the blood draws on Day 1a and 1b, Day 29, and Day 56.
- **Coordinating the blood draw** with the phlebotomist. **Blood samples should be collected before a meal, or at least 2 hours after a meal.** Record the time of the blood draw and whether there were any problems with blood draw procedures on the **Blood and Urine Collection form**.
- **Coordinating blood sample processing and LabCorp sample shipping** with your blood processing laboratory facility **and providing the lab staff with the LabCorp manual and collection kits.**
 - The blood samples must be brought to the processing facility and processed **immediately** after collection. All processing steps must be completed within **90** minutes of collection.
 - Once collected, ensure that the blood tubes remain upright at all times. Always place tubes in a sample rack or test tube stand within the transport cooler, not on their sides. Be careful to maintain an upright placement while samples are being transported to the lab and avoid shaking or jostling the samples during transport.
 - Once collected, ensure that blood tube remains at approximately 20°C (e.g., room temperature), unless directed to be shipped frozen. Blood is alive; extreme cold or heat will activate and/or damage blood cells. If transporting blood to your processing lab requires you to be outside in cold or heat, place tubes in a temperature-controlled container during transport.
- **Ensuring LabCorp samples are sent day-of** and the date and time sent is recorded along with the tracking number.
- Ensuring that the **Blood and Urine Processing** data collection form is completed. The study Research Coordinator needs to determine whether the **study Research Coordinator or Blood Processing Facility Staff is responsible for scanning** the cryovial and freezer storage rack barcodes and recording the sample information (volume, position, time to freezing, etc.) into the study data base. Obtain Vitals and Plasma Inflammatory Markers prior to collecting blood samples. Record the time the samples arrived at the lab on the Blood Collection & Processing form. Lab technicians will need to complete the rest of this form.
- Obtaining and preparing all blood collection, processing, and storage materials (see [Supply List](#)).
- Ensuring that all related data collection forms are completed in full and entered into the study database, including the Labs Exclusion Criteria at Screening and the Safety Lab Review Documentation after every safety labs report is available.

Associated Data Collection Form (s)	
Pre Blood Draw Health Screen	Blood and Urine Collection
Pregnancy Point-of-Care	Blood and Urine Processing
Safety Labs Review	Labs Exclusion Criteria

PRE-STUDY VISIT INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDY PARTICIPANTS: BLOOD SAMPLES

Blood Collection: Please provide study participants with the following information in writing **at least one week prior to the study visit and again on the day before the study visit.**

Instructions

You are scheduled for a blood draw on [*insert date scheduled*] at [*insert time scheduled*]. In order for us to get accurate measurements from your blood, you are asked to follow some guidelines.

- Starting 2 days before your draw, please try to drink plenty of water. Hydration is key to a quick and easy blood draw for both you and your phlebotomist!
- This is **not** a fasting blood draw, so please remember to regularly eat meals leading up to the blood draw. Ideally, your blood will be drawn before a meal or at least two hours after a meal.
- Please avoid using over-the-counter pain or cold medications **the week** before the study – for this visit, you would avoid using over-the-counter medications starting on [*insert day one week prior to specimen collection*]. This is because these medications may impact the levels of some of the substances that will be measured. Prescription medications should be taken according to the prescriber's instructions.
- Please be sure to get a good night's rest before your study visit.
- Please avoid rigorous exercise for 24 hours before your blood collection.
- Please don't smoke, vape, or use any other tobacco or nicotine products at least two hours prior to your study visit.
- Please do not use any marijuana or THC products on the day of your study visit.
- Please do not drink alcohol on the day of your study visit.
- You may maintain your usual caffeine intake.

BLOOD AND URINE SAMPLE VISIT PREP

Please review all collection instructions in the [LabCorp Manual](#).

A. Preparing the study participant

- Ask the study participant about their previous experiences with having their blood drawn.
- If the study participant expresses anxiety around the blood draw, a fear of needles, or some other concerns, take steps to address these concerns:
 - If the subject is concerned about risks of a blood draw inform the study participant that:
 - the amount of blood that is being collected is small, about 3 tablespoons. This volume is not enough to affect the study participant's body.
 - the main risks from a blood draw are bruising at the site of the blood draw, that the needle might hurt, and that some people may become light-headed or faint.
 - If the study participant has a history of feeling light-headed or fainting, or is concerned about this risk:
 - **Before the visit:**
 - Provide blood draw instructions to participants ahead of time. Fasting requirements are short, at only 2 hours. Have snacks on hand for participants if necessary, and remind participants to eat breakfast or have a light snack a few hours before the draw if possible.
 - It can be beneficial to have clinicians chat with the participant about worries surrounding the blood draw. This could be at screening or at a visit before the draw. Remind them we take less than 3 tablespoons of blood.
 - Inform the study participant that feeling light-headed, or fainting is a reflex response (the vasovagal reflex, or vasovagal syncope). Feeling light-headed or fainting is not due to the amount of blood that is taken.
 - **During the visit:**
 - Offer the subject either a sitting or lying down position.
 - Explain and have the study participant practice the Applied Muscle Tension Technique to use as a tool to prevent feeling light-headed or fainting.
 - Inform the phlebotomist about the history of feeling light-headed/fainting.
 - Have snacks, water, ice packs, and alcohol pads on hand in case of a fainting episode.
 - If the study participant expresses anxiety or distress about the blood draw:
 - Offer to distract the study participant during the blood draw by engaging in conversation, or allow them to distract themselves on their phone during the draw.
 - Offer to help the study participant discuss any of their concerns with the phlebotomist.
 - If participants begin to panic before or during the blood draw to the point where they seem to be in distress, it is up to the discretion of the RA or phlebotomist to call off the draw that day and evaluate if it should be rescheduled.

The Applied Muscle Tension Technique to Prevent Vasovagal Syncope

[Watch a video tutorial here.](#)

1. Done while seated, a few minutes prior to blood draw, and during the blood draw.
2. Tense muscles in legs, arm, and upper body. Hold for 10-15 seconds, or until you feel warmth rising in your face. (Do not tense the arm that is used for the blood draw during the blood draw.)
3. Release tension for 20-30 seconds.
4. Repeat 5 times prior to the blood draw, and during the blood draw.

B. Preparing the Collection Supplies

All blood and urine collection supplies will come from LabCorp. Please make sure you have the correct kits on-hand to complete a visit. The following instructions only apply to preparing for Proteomics and Drug level plasma collection on Days 1, 29, and 56.

1. Before you start, please double check that you have grabbed the LabCorp collection kit that corresponds to the correct timepoint!
2. If this is a Day1a and 1b visit, there will be two blood collection cryovials in each of those kits. If this is a Day 29 or Day 56 visit, four blood collection cryovials will be in your LabCorp collection kits.
 - a. Two cryovials will be for **proteomic plasma collection**.
 - i. Please write “P1” on one cryovial and “P2” on the other cryovial in permanent marker. Place these in the cardboard blood cryovial transportation box.
 - b. Two cryovials will be for **study drug level plasma collection**.
 - i. Please write “D1” on one cryovial and “D2” on the other cryovial in permanent marker. Place these in the cardboard blood cryovial transportation box.
 - ii. D1 will be your primary study drug level plasma sample, and D2 will be your back-up study drug level plasma sample.
3. If your site-specific protocol specifies that the Research Coordinator scans the cryovial barcodes into the database, then you will do so at this time. Scan them into the corresponding data entry fields in REDCap by placing the cursor into the field and scanning the barcode on the cryovial.
 - a. Please do not pre-scan in the freezer storage rack barcode. This should only be scanned in once the sample is collected, processed, and ready to be stored in the freezer.
 - b. If you are using the survey-enabled processing form in REDCap, you will not be able to pre-scan in any cryovials, and your processing team will have to do it for you.
4. Once all cryovials are prepared, the transportation rack will be ready for processing. To minimize the risk of sample mix-ups, it’s suggested that the cryovials are spaced a row apart.
5. If a site coordinator is not processing their own blood, it is preferred that the Blood Processing Facility staff directly enter data into REDCap either via typical REDCap access, or via a survey link to the Blood Collection & Processing form.
6. If the site is using a processing facility, the prepared cryovials in the transportation rack need to be brought to the processing laboratory along with the blood tubes (and possible urine samples) after collection. Study staff will need to verify the completed Blood & Urine Processing Form and obtain the now-empty transportation rack from the blood processing facility staff after all samples have been processed and stored correctly.

PRE BLOOD DRAW HEALTH SCREEN

The purpose of the **Pre Blood Draw Health Screen form** is to record any activities or conditions that may affect the participant's blood draw. This is completed at Day 1a and Day 1b, Day 29, Day 56, and in the case of early withdrawal. This form is not collected at Screening or Day 84, since only safety bloods are collected at those visits.

Remind the study participant that, "It's important to be honest; we understand sometimes a person can't avoid taking certain medications or just forgets about avoiding certain foods or medications. It's much better for the study to know about these things; so we understand."

A. When was Study Drug Taken

- Please record when the participant took their most recent dose of study medication.
 - If this is the Day 1 visit, you'll record the time of their very first dose in clinic.
 - If this is the Day 29 or Day 56 visit, please ask the participant the date and time of their most recent dose.

B. Sleep and Food

- Please be mindful of recording the correct date and time (on a 24 hour clock) when collecting this data.
 - All dates are recorded using a 24-hour clock (e.g. 11am = 11:00, 11pm = 23:00, 12am = 00:00, 12pm = 12:00).
 - For example, if the study participant went to bed at 11 pm and the study visit date is 11/05/2025, then the date for "went to bed" is 11/04/2025 (the day before the study visit date) and the time is 23:00. If the study participant went to bed at 1am, then the date for "went to bed" is 11/05/2025 (the same as the study visit date) and the time is 1:00.
- After recording the sleep and wake times, you will need to calculate the approximate hours slept prior to the study visit yourself and enter them into the proper field. This doesn't need to be exact, just the approximate hours slept.
 - If you're off by more than 1 hour, you'll get a warning asking you to check the math. This error checking is in place to catch large oversights in sleep data (ex: saying a participant slept 8 hours, but the form calculates sleep time as 32 hours because you input the wrong date.). This is not to test your mental math skills, just to double check the day and times are correct!
- You'll also record the last time the participant ate or drank anything with calories (not including diet beverages or water).
 - This blood draw has a 2-hour "fast," meaning participants need to wait at least two hours after eating or drinking anything with calories or sugar to get their blood drawn (diet drinks and water do not count).

C. Substance Use

- The next section asks participants to recall if they've ever used the following substances in their lifetime:
 - Tobacco or nicotine products (cigarettes, cigars, chewing tobacco, vaping, oral nicotine pouches, patches, gum, etc.)
 - Cannabis products (marijuana, weed, vaping, delta8, delta9, dabs, edibles, etc.)
 - Alcohol (beer, wine, "mixed drinks", spirits, etc.)

- If they answer “Yes” to any of these questions, a new set of questions will populate asking the frequency of use within the past month. You will ask them if in the past month they have used the substance “Never,” “Once or twice a month,” “Weekly,” or “Daily or almost daily”.
- If the answer is “Once or twice a month,” “Weekly,” or “Daily or almost daily,” you will ask the participant the date and time they last used the substance. This question only applies to nicotine and cannabis products.

D. Menstrual Cycle

- Ask the participant if they’ve ever had a menstrual period. You will choose either “Yes,” “No,” or “Male Participant” if the participant was assigned male at birth.
 - If “Yes,” ask the participant the date that their most recent menstrual cycle began (i.e. the first day of their most recent period).

E. Acute Inflammatory Conditions

- Record whether the participant has been sick in the last month. If yes, record the last date that they had any symptoms.
- Rate the participant’s acne via your observation using the [Investigator Global Assessment of Acne \(IGA\) Rating Scale](#).
- Ask the participant if they’ve had a sunburn in the last week. If yes, record the percent body area affected using the [“Rule of Nines”](#) sheet to calculate the percent area.
- Ask the participant if they’ve ever been diagnosed by a health professional, or self-diagnosed for the following health conditions:
 - Asthma, food allergy, environmental allergy, seasonal allergy, eczema, psoriasis, irritable bowel syndrome, tension headaches, migraine headaches, gingivitis, autoimmune disorder.
 - If they answer yes to an autoimmune disorder, please list the names of the disorders.

F. Preparing for the Blood Draw

- At the end of this form, please check off any strategies you used to prepare the participant for the blood draw.

Investigator Global Assessment of Acne (IGA) Rating Scale

Investigator Global Assessment of Acne (IGA) Rating Scale		
Grade 0 = 0	Grade 1 or Grade 2 = 1	Grade 3 or Grade 4 = 2
<p>Clear. Residual hyperpigmentation and erythema (redness) may be present.</p>	<p>Almost Clear: A few scattered blackheads or whiteheads and a few small papules.</p> <p>Mild-Easily recognizable, less than half of the face is involved. Some blackheads or whiteheads and some papules and pustules.</p>	<p>Moderate: More than half of the face is involved. Many blackheads or whiteheads, papules and pustules. One nodule may be present.</p> <p>Severe: Entire face is involved, covered with blackheads and whiteheads, numerous papules and pustules, and a few nodules and cysts.</p>

Rule of Nines Sunburn Rating Scale

Instructions: Ask study participant if they have a sunburn. If yes, ask the study participant to indicate what body areas are involved. Rate the percent of the body involved using the following scale. For example, if a study participant's arms and lower legs were sunburned in the back but not the front, the score would be $4.5+4.5+9+9=27$.

x

BLOOD & URINE COLLECTION FORM

This form is completed with information obtained during the blood draws and urine collection for same-day LabCorp shipments.

A. Study Visit

- Verify that you're in the correct form by selecting the study visit. If you select the incorrect study visit you'll receive an error warning.

B. Blood and Urine Sample Collection Times

- Record the blood sample collection date and time using a 24-hour clock.
- Record the urine sample collection date and time using a 24-hour clock.
 - A urine sample will not be collected on Day 1 post-dose, so this variable will not be visible in that form.
- After the blood draw ask the phlebotomist if there were any deviations from the guidelines and if so, record these on this form in the comments section.

C. Shipment of Processed Blood and Urine Specimens to LabCorp

- After samples have been processed, please scan in the LabCorp shipping label barcode.
- Then, after the shipment has been picked up or dropped off with the proper courier, please record the date and time (on a 24-hour clock) of the shipment.

PREGNANCY POINT OF CARE FORM

The Point-of-Care test for pregnancy will be conducted on Day 1, Day 29, Day 56, Day 89, and in the case of withdrawal. Please follow the instructions provided in the [LabCorp Manual](#) to conduct the test.

REDCap will automatically pull in the participant's sex assigned at birth from the sociodemographics form. If the participant is Female, the next questions will pop up. Please enter the lot number and expiration date of the POC test used.

Once you have the test results, please choose between "Pregnant" (for a positive test) or "Not Pregnant" (for a negative test) in the REDCap form. Results of the Pregnancy POC test may only be shared with the participant by the medical provider. If the test is positive, please contact your study doctor to discuss next steps.

BLOOD SAMPLE PROCESSING & STORAGE PROCEDURES

Please follow all collection and processing procedures as listed in the [LabCorp manual](#). The following are some extra reminders to be aware of.

A. Best Practices

All processing labs have their own guiding rules and practices, however there are practices that are standard across all lab settings. We understand that some staff may be processing biosamples for the first time, so this section is included for those unfamiliar with lab standards.

- Please use the resources below to learn about best pipetting practices.
 - [A Guide to Proper Pipetting](#) (Article)
 - [Micropipette Basics](#) (Video)
 - [Common Pipetting Mistakes](#) (Video)
- Please only fill blood storage cryovials to the requested amount. Overfilling, or pipetting more than the requested amount, may result in the lids "popping off" or the tube cracking. This is because liquid expands when it is frozen.
 - Overfilled cryovials with loose caps need to be corrected. We ask you to inspect cryovials for loose caps before shipping specimens. Overfilled cryovials with loose caps need to be addressed prior to shipping.
- Tools used in the lab should be **properly calibrated** and certified by specialized technicians at least once per year. Many universities and hospitals have contracts for centrifuge calibration and multivolume pipette calibration, but please reach out to us if you need assistance finding resources in your area.
 - **Improperly calibrated pipettes can lead to overfilling.**

B. Blood & Urine Processing Form

The questions in this form pertain to the processing of blood and urine samples. This form will be filled out in REDCap on Screening, Day 1 pre-dose, Day 1 post-dose, Day 29, Day 56, Day 84, and in the case of Early Withdrawal.

This form has been enabled as a survey. If the site chooses, they may send it as a survey to their biospecimen processing technician for direct entry into the data form.

- A. Study Visit
 - Verify that you're in the correct form by selecting the study visit. If you select the incorrect study visit you'll receive an error warning.
- B. Time Receive By Processing Lab
 - Record the date and time (using a 24-hour clock) that the blood tubes and urine samples arrived at the processing lab.
- C. Centrifuge Temperature
 - **All centrifugations will be done at room temperature.** To confirm this, record the temperature of the centrifuge and units.
 - If the temperature is too warm or too cold, you will get a warning that the centrifuge temperature is outside of expected room temperature range.
- D. Rate Hemolysis and Lipemia

- Evaluate the hemolysis and lipemia in the EDTA (purple top) blood collection tube after centrifugation, using the following scale.
 - Hemolysis is indicated by the color of the plasma (top layer of centrifuged tube) and Lipemia is indicated by the turbidity or cloudiness of the plasma.

Hemolysis Rating Scale Guide

Lipemia Rating Scale Guide

E. Proteomics Plasma Samples

- Cryovial barcodes for P1 and P2 should be scanned into their respective fields if they haven't been done already.
- Follow the processing guidelines in the LabCorp manual, then record the volume of the processed samples.
- Follow the storage guidelines outlines below. Make sure to properly record the position and scan in the freezer rack barcode into the form.
- Record the time to freezer for the proteomic plasma samples.

F. Study Drug Level Plasma Samples

- Cryovial barcodes for D1 and D2 should be scanned into their respective fields if they haven't been done already.
- Follow the processing guidelines in the LabCorp manual, then record the volume of the processed samples.
- Follow the storage guidelines outlines below. Make sure to properly record the position and scan in the freezer rack barcode into the form.
- Record the time to freezer for the study drug plasma samples.

Before saving the form, record the Storage freezer ID so you remember where they are stored, and record any processing issues or protocol violations in the form.

C. Blood Sample Storage Guidelines

Blood sample storage racks are provided by the UNC Biospecimen Core team. Each site will be shipped one Proteomic Plasma freezer storage rack and two Study Drug freezer storage racks. Additional Study Drug racks will be shipped upon request as needed. All blood sample cryovials will be provided by LabCorp.

Samples should be stored from left to right (positions 1-9) before moving on to the next row. Please be extra attentive when recording the storage position of each sample to ensure that you are recording the correct storage position.

In the case of low-volume draws, it's always preferred to process as much as possible and split the resulting plasma between the cryovials. However, if for whatever reason one cryovial is empty, you should not store the empty cryovial in the storage rack. Because multiple participant samples will be stored in the same row, as long as the correct positions and rack barcode are recorded in REDCap, that will be sufficient for data collections purposes.

Proteomic Plasma Freezer Storage Rack

On Day 1a, Day 29, and Day 56 (and in the case of early withdrawal), **two** cryovials of Proteomic Plasma will be processed and stored in the Proteomic Plasma Freezer Storage Rack (depicted below). The samples will be labeled P1 (the primary sample) and P2 (the back-up sample). Ideally, P1 samples will be stored in odd-numbered positions, and P2 samples will be stored in even-numbered positions. This rack can hold up to 81 samples and will be used for the entirety of the study. It will be shipped at the end of follow-up.

Drug Level Plasma Freezer Storage Rack

On Day 1b, Day 29, and Day 56 (and in the case of early withdrawal), **two** cryovials of Study Drug Level Plasma will be processed and stored in the Study Drug Level Freezer Storage Rack (depicted below). The samples will be labeled D1 (the primary sample) and D2 (the back-up sample). Ideally, D1 samples will be stored in odd-numbered positions, and D2 samples will be stored in even-numbered positions. This rack can hold up to 25 samples and will be used for the entirety of the study. All D1 samples for a participant will be shipped on Day 56.

SAFETY LABS REVIEW

Safety Labs should be available within the LabCorp Portal within 24 hours of collection. Sites are responsible for having the prescribers review and sign off on results within 72 hours of receipt either via the portal or via printed report.

You must document that this review happened in REDCap via the Safety Lab Review Documentation Form. Select whether or not the report was reviewed, list the date, and the method of review (either LabCorp portal or printed copy). If printed, upload a copy of the document to REDCap.

At Screening, the results of the safety lab must be input into the Labs Exclusion Criteria form as soon as the report is reviewed by the study doctor.

- Record whether there is a clinically significant laboratory test abnormality and of clinical relevance at Screening prior to Day -1, unless normalized on single repeat, as determined by the Investigator.
- Record whether there is severe renal impairment as indicated by an estimated creatinine clearance less than 30 mL per minute at Screening prior to Day -1.
- Record whether there is a positive drug screen for cocaine, opioid, PCP, amphetamine or heroin at Screening prior to Day-1, unless associated with documented prescription use. If yes, select whether they were prescribed or not prescribed.
- Record the result of the pregnancy blood test.
- Ascites and Hepatic Encephalopathy will be automatically populated from the Limited Physical and Neurological Examination Screen form.
- Record the ranges of the total bilirubin, serum albumin, and normalized prothrombin (INR).
- Child Pugh Score will automatically populate.

SAMPLE STORAGE QC

Both blood and saliva samples should be periodically checked in the freezer to ensure correct storage procedures are being maintained. It's suggested that each time you place a newly processed cryovial into the freezer rack, you should do a quick visual scan of the other cryovials in the rack for any loose caps, cracks, or other deviations.

If any SOP deviations occur with the cryovials before, during, or after processing, please add a **field comment to the barcode** of the cryovial in REDCap and notify the Genetics and Fluids team ASAP. Click on the speech bubble button to the left of the barcode field, and enter the deviation into the comment.

Sample Aliquots:	
Whole blood sample 1 cryotube barcode <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="text" value="987654321"/>
Whole blood sample 1 volume (mL) <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="text" value="1.2"/>
Whole blood sample 1 position in cryotube rack. <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="text" value="B1"/>

Some examples include the following:

- "cryovial overfilled, cap loose"
- "cryovial cracked"

Multiple field comments can be added to one cryovial if necessary.

Field Comment Log

This pop-up displays all the field comments for the record and field specified below. Users with access to data entry forms may leave one or more comments on any field on a data collection instrument, after which the balloon icon will stay lit up to signify that comments exist for that field for this record. All field comments for all records/fields can also be viewed, keyword searched, and filtered on the [Field Comment Log](#) page in this project. NOTE: If you wish to prevent all users in this project from editing or deleting field comments below, see the [Additional Customizations](#) popup on the Project Setup page.

Record ID: **NC00002**
Event: **Baseline (Arm 1: CHR)**
Field: **chrblood_wb1id** ("Whole blood sample 1 cryotube barcode")

	Date/Time	User	Comments
	01-22-2024 11:58	rb2362	cryovial overfilled, cap loose
	01-22-2024 11:59	rb2362	<input type="text" value="freeze-thaw at xC for x minutes"/>

BLOOD AND SALIVA SAMPLE SHIPPING

The ProCAN clinical trials will use a central lab via **LabCorp** to process all safety labs. Please refer to the [LabCorp manual](#) for same-day shipping requirements for blood tubes and urine samples. After sites have processed the EDTA tube(s), **two proteomics aliquots** will be stored in **Proteomics Rack** and **two drug level aliquots** will be stored in **Study Drug Sample Rack(s)**.

The D1 primary aliquots stored in the **Study Drug Sample Rack** will be shipped **on Day 56 for each participant** on dry ice to a **TBD** facility for drug level analyses. Sites will pull the participant's D1 samples from the Study Drug Sample Rack, and ship in a **TBD** container on dry ice. The aliquots stored in the **Proteomics Rack** will be sent at the end of follow-ups to **TBD** for proteomic analyses. The samples stored in the **Saliva Racks** will be sent at the end of follow-ups to Salimetrics for cortisol analysis. Sites must ensure that they have enough freezer space to store samples for at least six months post-recruitment in case of delays.

The core will work with you to prepare the shipment and to ensure that the samples are shipped securely.

A. General Shipping Procedures

Pre-shipment prep

Shipping supplies

- a. Before you compile the shipment, you need to make sure you have the following supplies on hand:
 - i. **New** insulated foam shipper. We recommend a **TBD** (interior) container which can ship no more than 8 racks. (This is equivalent to a **TBD** exterior measurement.)
 1. Some recommended brands are [Sonoco Thermosafe](#) distributed by Fisher Scientific, [Therapak](#) from Avantor/VWR, and [ULINE](#) are some reputable brands of shippers. Depending on how many racks you intend to ship at one time, you may choose a slightly larger or smaller shipper.
 2. Please purchase a new shipper instead of re-using as FedEx may not accept gently used boxes depending on the quality. **On average, each site will need to purchase about TBD insulated shipping containers to use throughout the first clinical trial.**
 - ii. [Dry Ice labels](#) (Dangerous Goods, Category 9, UN1845)
 - iii. Human Exempt Specimen [label](#) (or indicate by writing on the outermost box).
 - i. One Ziploc bag per rack.
 - ii. Absorbent material (paper towels, Kimwipes, or cotton rounds).
 - iii. Clear shipping or packing tape.
 - iv. At least 10kg (~22lbs) of dry ice in pellet form. The dry ice should be the last item obtained, preferably the day of shipping, so make sure to plan in advance.
 1. Best practice is to plan for ~5kg (10lbs) of ice per 24 hours of travel. We intend to overnight ship packages, however we advise to pack enough ice for 48 hours in case of any shipping issues.
 2. If you need to order dry ice a day in advance, or believe it may take time to pack your samples, please factor this into the amount you purchase. Without an ice chest, about 1lb of dry ice will sublime every 2 hours.
 - v. Dry ice can cause 3rd degree burns when exposed to skin. Please wear cryo-protective gloves when handling.

Cryovial QC & manifest creation

- a. Before you are allowed to ship samples, you must ensure that all cryovial queries have been fixed in the REDCap database. Please also perform a visual check of the cryovials you would like to ship. While on dry ice, remove the rack lid and perform a visual check of the cryovials and rack. Make sure the caps are secure (pushed down ~50%) and that there are no cracks in the cryovials or rack itself.
 - i. If there are any issues with the cryovials, please refer to [Sample Storage QC](#) to properly handle and document them. Please contact your Genetics & Fluids core team right away if you have any cryovials that are not in ideal shipping conditions.
 - ii. Ensure that all cryovials contain some sample. Empty cryovials should not be shipped or exist in the REDCap database.
- b. Manifests will need to be created so the receiving lab can know which participant's sample is in what position. **Manifest creation and guidelines will be released at a later date.**

2. Compiling your shipment

- a. It is preferred that the site team compiles the shipment instead of a processing lab. However, if your hospital or university requires you to use a third party outside of ProCAN staff, please let the Core team know ASAP. This will require more frequent communication between all parties.
- b. Please obtain ship date approval from your Genetics & Fluids team. Please also provide an approximate timeframe so a team member can make themselves available for questions and to create the shipping label.
- c. Final manifests will be sent to the receiving lab. **More details to be released at a later date.**
- d. **On your approved ship date, email your Genetics & Fluids contact with the following:**
 1. Number of shippers you will be sending.
 2. Outer package dimensions of each shipper.
 3. Approximate package weight (lb or kg) of each shipper.
 4. Amount of dry ice used in each shipper.
 5. The address you are shipping from and a contact number.
 6. Whether you will be scheduling a pick-up by FedEx or driving the box to a drop-off location.
 - If you will be dropping off, please include the address of the FedEx storefront you will be using.
- e. The Genetics and Fluids team will create your FedEx label based on the above info and email it to your site.
- f. Begin to compile the shipment. If you are inexperienced with packing samples for shipment, [please watch this packing tutorial here](#). If you would prefer, you may your shipment while on a Zoom call with a member of the Genetics & Fluids team.
 - i. Place a layer of dry ice on the bottom of the insulated shipper (~5in or 2.5cm).
 - ii. Place each sample storage rack into a plastic Ziploc bag with absorbent material such as paper towels. There should be enough absorbent material in each bag to properly absorb all liquid contents, should any cryovials leak. Securely seal the Ziploc bag, ensuring that excess air is squeezed out when the bag is sealed.
 - iii. Place the sealed bags containing sample storage racks in the middle of the shipper on top of the dry ice.

- iv. Place dry ice on top of and around the sides of the sealed bags containing the sample storage racks. The sample storage racks should be covered on all sides.
- v. Place the lid on the Styrofoam box. Ensure that there is no dry ice preventing the lid from fitting as it should. If necessary, you may use 1 or two small pieces of tape to secure the lid to the Styrofoam shipper, but do not completely seal the shipper along the lid; gas must be able to escape as dry ice sublimates.
- vi. Place a printed copy of the completed manifest on top of the closed Styrofoam box within the cardboard box.
- vii. Use packaging tape to securely close the outer cardboard box. Again, ensure you are not sealing off all gaps so dry ice can sublimate. We suggest using the taping pattern indicated in the diagram to the left.
- viii. Ensure that a dry ice declaration sticker and either a sticker or writing indicating “Exempt Human Specimen” are displayed on the outer cardboard box and filled out properly. Follow any additional requirements of your institution or country.
- ix. The shipping label will be sent via email to the site. Print & affix the label to the outside of the cardboard box. Do not use a plastic label pouch on the shipment, the entire surface of the printed label should be covered in tape.
 1. **All stickers and labels should be clearly displayed on one side of the box. (See image to the left.) However, stickers and labels cannot touch.**
- x. After you receive the FedEx label, schedule a FedEx pick up, or proceed to your indicated FedEx location. To schedule pickups, call 1.800.GoFedEx or 1.800.463.3339.
 1. Please do not leave your package unattended until your shipment is picked up by FedEx.

3. Ensuring chain of custody from site to second location

- a. Once FedEx picks up the package, please reply to your manifest email sent two days prior to confirm pick-up and provide the tracking number.
- b. More requirements will be released at a later date.

General Start-Up Requirements

A. Certification

Each site must provide the Biospecimen Fluids Core must indicate which research staff member is responsible for each collection, processing, and shipping task in the Delegation of Authority Log. Each staff member listed must have attended or watched the training and passed the associated certification task to collect the data below. It is expected that at least one staff member will be trained and certified in Vitals, Saliva, and Blood and Urine Collection prior to the SIV. It's recommended to have a back-up staff member trained in case of staff turnover or illness.

Vitals Collection Certification

Any staff member that will collect blood pressure, heart rate, and temperature for REDCap data entry must be certified. This includes any PIs, MDs, RNs, coordinators and research assistants that will collect and enter this data into the intended collection forms.

1. Watch the Vitals Collection Training Video on SharePoint.
2. Record and submit a video demonstrating proper blood pressure, heart rate, and temperature collection according to our SOPs.
 - i. Staff will be assessed on the criteria outlined in the Vitals Grading Rubric on SharePoint.
 - ii. Submit your collected data in the Vitals Certification Form on SharePoint.
 - iii. Upload your video to your site's specified SharePoint folder. Please make sure your name is included in the video file name.

Saliva Collection Certification

Any staff member that will collect and store saliva samples must be certified. This includes any PIs, MDs, RNs, coordinators and research assistants that will collect and enter this data into the intended collection forms.

1. Watch the Saliva Collection Training Video on SharePoint.
2. Complete and submit the Saliva Certification Quiz.

Blood and Urine Collection Certification

Any staff member that will collect, process, store, or ship blood or urine samples must be certified. This includes any PIs, MDs, RNs, coordinators, research assistants, and laboratory technicians that will collect and enter this data into the intended collection forms. Phlebotomists or nurses that are only drawing blood do not need to complete this training.

1. Watch the LabCorp Blood and Urine Collection Training Video on SharePoint.
2. Complete the LabCorp online training.
3. Watch the Blood and Urine Follow-Up Training Video on SharePoint.
4. Complete and submit the Blood and Urine Certification Quiz.

Additional Trainings and Certifications

Sites should have at least one member of the team (ideally the coordinator) review these materials. Documentation and certification is not required, but strongly encouraged at a site level.

1. Watch the Biospecimen REDCap Training on SharePoint.

- i. There is no associated certification quiz, but please consider how your site will operate and who will have the responsibility of filling out each of the Biospecimen forms.
2. Sites should also consider the following in their Biospecimen workflow:
- i. How will your site transport the blood, urine, or saliva to the processing facility and/or the freezers? Who will be responsible?
 - ii. If using an external or core lab for processing, the Biospecimen Core would prefer to have a direct line of communication in case we need to inform processors of any changes regarding the blood processing protocol.
 - iii. If using an external or core lab for processing, how will they enter in processing data? Will you send the form as a survey, or will you attend processing with them to data enter?
 - iv. Who will be responsible for shipping LabCorp samples on the day-of collection?
 - v. Who will be responsible for making sure dry ice is available at Screening and Day 56?
 - vi. Who will be responsible for communicating results and reports to the prescriber or PI?

B. Supply and Equipment List

Procedure	Item	ProCAN
Height	Stadiometer	To be purchased by site, suggested brands available upon request.
Weight	Scale	To be purchased by site, suggested brands available upon request.
Vitals	Blood pressure/heart rate monitor + child-size cuff	To be purchased by site if not using calibrated hospital equipment: Omron 10 Series Upper Arm Blood Pressure Monitor.
Vitals	Tympanic Thermometer	To be purchased by site if not using calibrated hospital equipment: Braun ThermoScan 5 Ear Thermometer.
Saliva Collection and Storage	Saliva Collection Aids ¹ by Salimetrics 2.0mL Screw-top cryovials by Thermo Fisher Scientific Transportation and storage racks for 2.0mL cryovials by Thermo Fisher Scientific	Provided to sites by Biospecimen Core team (UNC). ProNET sites should re-use their transportation racks.
Saliva Collection	Hard-Sided Sample Transportation Cooler (approx. 4qt)	To be purchased by site. Suggested models include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4.8qt chest cooler via Grainger • 4qt mini cooler via Igloo Coolers • 5qt Igloo cooler via Amazon
Saliva Collection	Nitrile gloves Permanent marker Disinfectant wipes Underpads	Use standard lab supplies; suggestion provided upon request.
Saliva Collection & Blood Processing	1D/2D/Data Matrix Barcode Scanner (with any needed accessories such as cradle or cable)	To be purchased by sites. Suggested models include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brady Code Reader 950 via Fisher Scientific • Brady CR950 wired via Avantor/VWR • TEEMI 2d barcode scanner via Amazon
Saliva & Blood Storage	-80C Ultra-low freezer equipped with internal monitoring system OR added on external monitoring system	Use standard lab equipment; suggestion provided upon request.
Phlebotomy	Nitrile gloves 21G Butterfly Needles Vacutainer Holders Tourniquets Alcohol Pads Gauze Pads	Use standard lab supplies; suggestion provided upon request.

¹ Saliva Collection aids are a patented product created by Salimetrics. They are hard plastic tubing that click into 2mL cryovials and act as a straw for passive drool collection.

	Medical Tape Sharps Containers	
Blood Processing	1000uL Multivolume pipettor 1000uL Pipette Tips 15mL Sterile screw-top centrifuge tubes Room-temperature swing bucket centrifuge	Use standard lab supplies; suggestion provided upon request.
Blood Processing and Storage	1mL screw-top cryovials	Provided to sites by LabCorp.
Blood Processing and Storage	Transportation and storage racks for 1mL cryovials	Provided to sites by Biospecimen Core team (UNC).
Sample Shipments	Insulated shipper	Day-of shippers for blood and urine will be provided by LabCorp. More info about end of study shipments to be provided at a later date.
Sample Shipments	Dry ice	Coordinated by site. Needed for each Screening visit sample shipment and at end of study shipments.

D. Equipment Calibration Requirements

Regular equipment calibration is a very important part of clinical trials to ensure the accuracy and reliability of collected data. Sites will be responsible for getting equipment calibrated regularly, and for providing proof of calibration to the Northwell project managers. Proof of calibration may include a picture of the certification sticker on the equipment with next due date, or a copy of the calibration report. This list does not include everything that needs to be calibrated yearly for ProCAN, just the equipment that will be used for Biospecimen data collection.

Some sites may be prohibited from using or purchasing unauthorized equipment on site. Sites may also choose to use clinic or hospital equipment that is regularly calibrated instead of purchasing recommended equipment. If sites will not be purchasing the recommended equipment from ProCAN, they must provide this information in writing to the following people:

- Priya Matneja (pmatneja@northwell.edu)
- Adisa Velovic (avelovic@northwell.edu)
- Diana Perkins (diana_perkins@med.unc.edu)
- Rachel Bleggi (rachel_bleggi@med.unc.edu)

Vitals Equipment

The following equipment used to measure vitals must be calibrated regularly.

- Physician scale
 - Proof of calibration required for each scale used.
 - If your site does not conduct regular calibration on your scale, the site will undergo a reliability test.
 - Scale Reliability Test
 - On Day 1, two staff members will take turns weighing themselves on the same scale five times. Person 1 will step on and record weight 1, then Person 2 will step on and record weight 1, and they will continue switching off until all five weights are recorded.
 - The same two people will repeat this process on Day 2 at approximately the same time.

- These recorded values will be submitted to the Biospecimen Core, and the core will calculate the coefficient of variance. If less than 1%, the scale will be determined to be reliable, and will be approved for use in the clinical trial.
- Please use the Scale Reliability Microsoft Form found on the ProCAN SharePoint site.
- Tympanic thermometer
 - If a site is using a tympanic thermometer provided by their institution, proof of regular calibration is required.
 - If sites are purchasing the ProCAN recommended Braun Thermscan 5 Ear Thermometer:
 - According to the user manual, the thermometer is initially calibrated at the time of manufacture.^{xi}
 - Sites are responsible for calibrating this thermometer yearly, or if a site cannot find a calibration service, or doesn't want to pay for calibration, they may purchase the thermometer new again.
- Blood pressure monitor
 - If a site is using a blood pressure monitor provided by their institution, proof of regular calibration is required.
 - If sites are purchasing the ProCAN recommended Omron 10 Series Upper Arm Blood Pressure Monitor:
 - Omron Healthcare abides by clinical validation as outlined on their company website. All listed validated monitors are initially calibrated at the time of manufacture.^{xii}
 - Sites are responsible for calibrating this blood pressure monitor yearly, or if a site cannot find a calibration service, or doesn't want to pay for calibration, they may purchase the blood pressure monitor new again.

Biospecimen Collection and Storage Equipment

Based on general best practices for biospecimen labs, the following equipment used to collect, process, and store biospecimen must be calibrated regularly. If a site has any questions or concerns, please reach out to your Biospecimen Core contacts.

- Multivolume Pipette
- Swing-bucket centrifuge
- Ultra-low -80C freezer
- Freezer monitor (if not internal to the freezer)

E. Biospecimen Storage Supplies

Blood and urine collection tubes, processing vials, as well as same-day shipping materials will be provided by LabCorp to your site. **Saliva collection/storage materials, and blood plasma storage racks will be purchased by the UNC Biospecimen Core team and sent to each site.** Materials will be shipped in bulk to the site before the SIV, and it will be expected that sites will be responsible for managing their materials throughout the length of the clinical trial.

A single shipment will contain most of the blood storage and saliva collection/storage for the entire clinical trial, plus a few extra items in case of training or loss. **Each site will be responsible for pulling materials from their shipment as needed** (i.e. pulling 3 Saliva Collection Aids and 3 saliva cryovials on Day -1.) Additional materials needed for each visit are listed in the [Supply List](#) and will be purchased by the sites or provided by LabCorp. Proteomics blood storage racks will hold 81 samples. Study drug level blood storage racks will hold 25 samples. Saliva storage racks will hold 48 samples. **If a site runs out or misplaces any supplies, please contact the Genetics & Fluids Core team ASAP to ask about a replacement.**

Components of a Shipment	
Item	# of Units
Nalgene barcoded freezer storage racks for 1mL blood cryovials	3
Transportation box for blood cryovials	1
Saliva Collection Aids	~100
2mL screw-top saliva cryovials with matrix barcode	~100
Nunc barcoded freezer storage racks for 2mL saliva cryovials	2
Transportation rack for 2.0mL saliva cryovials*	1
Saliva practice kit	1
Laminated signs and workflows	1
<i>*Sites that were previously in ProNET may continue to use their previous transportation racks, and will not be shipped new ones unless asked.</i>	

- One (1) barcoded freezer storage rack for blood will be used to store all of the processed Proteomics plasma. This rack will be shipped once at the end of follow-up.
- Two (2) barcoded freezer storage racks for blood will be shipped to store the Study Drug plasma samples.
- One (1) blood sample box and one (1) saliva sample rack are to be re-used at each visit as “transportation racks.” The purpose of these racks is to be used while preparing sample vials for study visits (e.g. while hand-labelling vials and scanning barcodes into the database) and for sample transportation (e.g. in the ice cooler for saliva).
- Saliva cryovials should be kept in a sealed plastic bag and should always be handled with clean, gloved hands. It is crucial to not contaminate these materials.
- Sites must ensure that they do not accidentally discard any of these items.

F. Production and Distribution of Supplies

NOTE: *The following procedures describe the kit production procedures that take place at the ProCAN Genetics & Fluids core only. These procedures **do not** apply to the ProCAN sites.*

Prevent contamination of supplies:

- Always wear clean gloves when handling kit materials.
- Always reseal bags or containers of materials when not in use.

How to make the first shipment:

- The components of each kit must be checked for correctness by at least two people.
- Each bag of supplies must be contained within a sealed plastic bag.
 - Saliva cryovials and Saliva Collection Aids should each be contained in their own plastic bag and labeled.
 - Label each of the 3 blood sample storage racks with freezer safe labels and then place them both into plastic bags. Seal the plastic bag securely.
 - Label each of the 2 saliva sample storage racks with freezer safe labels and then place them both into one plastic bag. Seal the plastic bag securely.
 - One blood transportation rack and one saliva transportation rack labeled with a freezer safe label (if applicable).
 - One practice kit with 5 cryovials and 5 saliva collection aids should be contained in one plastic bag labeled "For practice use only."
- Place all bags of supplies into a box. Use bubble wrap as needed to ensure materials will not damage in transit.
- Include laminated SOP tips.

Distribution of Supplies

The ProCAN Genetics & Fluids Core team will be responsible for the following:

- Purchasing the kit supplies listed above.
- Production and shipment of kits.
- Obtaining site addresses for shipment.
- Providing the shipment tracking number and anticipated delivery date to the site.
- Following up with the site to receive email confirmation of receipt and alerting the ProNET Coordination Team and the site PI to a lack of response if necessary.
- Updating the ProCAN Kit Shipment Tracker with the following information as it is available:
 - Shipping Address
 - Date Shipped
 - Tracking Number
 - Date Received
 - Date of site request for kit shipment (Shipment 2 onward)

ProCAN Sites will be responsible for the following:

- Tracking their on-site ProCAN biospecimen kit inventory.
- Notifying the ProCAN Genetics & Fluids core when they are in need of additional supplies.

- Tracking the shipment using the provided tracking number until receipt of shipment.
- Confirming shipment contents and notifying the ProCAN Genetics & Fluids core upon shipment receipt.

Future Shipments of Supplies

Sites will be required to reach out to the Core team if they need additional saliva collection supplies, or blood and saliva storage supplies. It is unlikely that a site will need to request a second shipment of other supplies as the first shipment should have enough to last them throughout the clinical trial. Supplies in these shipments do not expire. However, in the case of contamination or loss, sites are responsible for emailing the Genetics & Fluids core team with the number of requested supplies. The Core team will send an acknowledgement of the request within 2 business days and the shipment of kits will be shipped to the site within 3 weeks of the request, as the Core team will not be keeping stock on hand to fulfill orders.

Sites will be asked to provide an updated shipping address each time they are shipped supplies. The shipment tracking number and anticipated delivery date will be provided to the site once the shipment has been sent. Sites should note that shipments may be delivered prior to or after the anticipated delivery date, so they should track the shipment continuously until shipment receipt. Once the site receives the shipment, they will be required to confirm receipt of the shipment and the presence of all kit components via email to the ProCAN Genetics & Fluids core.

Site Location	Shipping Method	Shipping Time
North America	USPS Priority	3 business days

Freezer Temperature Monitoring

A. Monthly Freezer Logs

- Monthly freezer logs are an important part of most clinical trials to keep track of sample and/or drug quality.
- Sites will be required to use an electronic freezer monitoring system for each of the freezers used in this study.
 - If you're unsure if your site has an electronic monitoring system, please talk with your lab manager.
 - If your site is in need of purchasing an electronic monitoring system, suggestions can be found in the supply section below, and the Core team can discuss other options with you if needed.
- Sites will be required to upload freezer logs to **SharePoint at the end of each month**.
 - Most electronic monitors have standard monthly reports, however if you have any questions about how to generate these, please contact the Core team.
 - Here is an example of what a monthly report log might look like:

B. Freezer Deviation Reporting

- Ultra-low freezers (including -80°C) will fluctuate a few degrees above or below set-point as part of normal use. However, in the case of a fluctuation outside of expected values, and it's important to document the excursion for sample quality assurance.
- The freezer temperature may vary no more than by +15°C from -80°C and should remain at or near the set point (not near the maximum) the majority of the time. Any excursions above -65°C must be recorded.

	Set Point	Maximum/Warmest
Ultra-Low Freezer	-80°C	-65°C

- Freezer excursions will be recorded within REDCap. In the Freezer Deviation floating form you will indicate whether or not a participant's samples experienced an excursion. Please fill out this form as soon as you become aware of the excursion.
 - Indicate the highest temperature recorded on the freezer log during the excursion time.
 - Record the date and time the freezer excursion started (when it first became warmer than -65°C).
 - Record the date and time the freezer excursion ended (when it first cooled back down to -65°C).
 - Record the number of this participant's study drug samples that were affected and scan each barcode. Remember, if more than one participant was affected, you will need to record this information again on their REDCap form.
 - Record whether or not the proteomics and saliva racks were affected as well. If ye, please scan in the rack barcode.

C. Emergency Freezer Back-up

Sites should have protocols in place for freezer malfunctions and power outages. Make sure you have at least one primary and one secondary option available to you in case of emergencies. If you are renting freezer space from a larger core lab, they should already have protocols in place, so please make sure you are aware of them. Some examples may include:

- Moving samples to a secondary -80C freezer either owned by your team or borrowed from another group temporarily.
- Moving your samples to a Styrofoam cooler with dry ice. Replenish dry ice every 24 hours.
- Check with your university or hospital HVAC team if they have freezers available to rent in emergency situations.
- Find a vendor in your city that offers -80C rentals.

ONGOING QC

A. ProCAN Fluid Biospecimen Monthly Meeting

Our team will be hosting a **TBD monthly meeting** to discuss implementation obstacles and frequently asked questions related to biospecimen collection and processing. They are held on **TBD at TBD**. If you would like the meeting invite, please email Rachel Bleggi (rachel_bleggi@med.unc.edu). Recordings of the meeting will be uploaded to SharePoint.

B. Fidelity to Study Protocols

TBD retraining

C. Data Monitoring

Value ranges are provided for most numerical data points. If entered values fall outside of the provided range, the data will be flagged for verification. In addition to the quality assurance checks implemented by the CT-DPACC (e.g. ensuring that date of assessment after consent date), the following quality assurance checks will be implemented:

Form	Data Quality Checks
Crosscheck Reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study Visit Dates of Plasma Inflammatory Markers, Blood Collection and Processing, Pregnancy POC, and Vitals Form should match where applicable.
Height and Weight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height must be greater than or equal to 1.2 meters and less than or equal to 2.2 meters. Weight must be greater than 36 kg and less than 136 kg.
Vitals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blood pressure cuff must be placed on the participant's non-dominant arm. Sp chr vitals_handed cannot be the same as chr vitals_cuff. If chr vitals_systolic_1 is greater than or equal to 140 or chr vitals_diastolic_1 is greater than or equal to 90, a warning will pop up with instructions to wait 5 minutes, repeat protocol, and measure again. If chr vitals_systolic is greater than 140 and less than 180, or if chr vitals_diastolic is greater than 90 or less than 120, a warning will inform that the value is in the hypertensive range and to inform the prescriber. If chr vitals_systolic is greater 180, or if chr vitals_diastolic is greater 120, a warning will inform that the value is in the hypertensive crisis and to inform the prescriber immediately. If chr vitals_temptype does not equal "Tympanic" then a warning will pop up specifying protocol requirements. If chr vitals_bodytemp is less than 96, the warning requests coordinator to measure again. If chr vitals_bodytemp is greater than 100.4, the warning requests coordinator to inform provider of elevated body temp.
Saliva Sample Collection for Cortisol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date participant went to bed and woke up cannot be before assessment date.
Pre Blood Draw Health Screen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date participant went to bed and woke up cannot be before assessment date.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time participant last ate cannot be after the date of assessment. • Time participant last used tobacco products and nicotine products cannot be after the date of assessment. • Date of last menstrual period cannot be after the date of assessment. • Date of last symptoms cannot be after the date of assessment.
Blood and Urine Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study date selection must match current form. • Date of blood and urine shipment cannot be before collection date/time.
Pregnancy Point-of-Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pregnancy test must be performed if participant is assigned female at birth. • If pregnancy test is positive, warning boxes that participant is ineligible and coordinator must inform prescriber and PI of positive test.
Blood and Urine Processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study date selection must match current form.
Safety Lab Review Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If labs were not reviewed by prescriber, warning will request that they are reviewed.
Labs Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If pregnancy test is positive, warning boxes that participant is ineligible and coordinator must inform prescriber and PI of positive test. • If Child Pugh score is greater than or equal to 7, then warning will inform that participant has met exclusionary criteria.
Shipping Plasma for Study Drug Levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment date cannot precede date of consent.
Freezer Deviation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If warmest temperature is recorded as a positive number (above 0), warning pops up.

In addition, CT-DPACC will conduct on-site monitoring visits where, for 25% of the subject sample, all collected data and any file notes will be reviewed on-site in order to ensure that the study is conducted in line with the protocol and the SOPs. Any file notes indicating issues with assessments described in the current SOP which are not documented within REDCap will be shared with the site study team and Fluid Biomarker Domain Expert Team leads.

APPENDIX

A. LabCorp training slides and manual

The LabCorp manual and eLearning trainings are available on the Investigator Portal at <https://xip.labcorp.com/login>. If you have not received an “Xcellerate Investigator Portal” email notification from XIPUserAdminNoReply@labcorp.com, please reach out to Rachel Bleggi to coordinate access.

LabCorp training slides are available on SharePoint.

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ⁱⁱ Nutrition Assessment: A Comprehensive Guide for Planning Intervention by M.D. Simko, C. Cowell, and J.A. Gilbride (eds.), p.77, Aspen Publishers, Inc., 1984.

ⁱⁱⁱ American Heart Association News. (2024, June 25). The rules for measuring blood pressure – and why they exist. Retrieved from American Heart Association: <https://www.heart.org/en/news/2024/06/25/the-rules-for-measuring-blood-pressure-and-why-they-exist>

^{iv} <https://map.ama-assn.org/resources/office-bp-measurement-infographic>

^v Device.report. (2023). *Microlife BP3GX1-5A blood pressure monitor user guide*. device.report. <https://device.report/manual/3799668>

^{vi} PULLEN, RICHARD L. JR. RN, EDD. Using an ear thermometer. *Nursing* 33(5):p 24, May 2003.

^{vii} Bontinen, K., Metcalf, B., Stephen, L.-A., Hughes, M., Verkuyl, M., Lapum, J. L., Garcia, W., St-Amant, O., & Tan, A. (2021, January 22). *Tympanic temperature*. Vital Sign Measurement Across the Lifespan 2nd Canadian Edition.
<https://opentextbc.ca/vitalsignmeasurement/chapter/tympanic-temperature/>

^{viii} <https://nursekey.com/vital-signs-5/>

^{ix} Kawaishi, Y. (2024, July 20). *Salivary gland massage*. Physio Visuals: Illustrated Exercise, Stretching, and Rehabilitation Guides. <https://physiovisuals.com/salivary-gland-massage/>

^x <https://biology-forums.com/index.php?action=gallery;sa=view;id=8772>

^{xi} https://www.braunhealthcare.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/irt6020_6030_6500_6510_om_a007471r1_r4_20jun22_manual.pdf

^{xii} <http://omronhealthcare.com/clinical-validation>